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DETERMINANTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIAN YOUTH SERVICES: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF STRATEGIC COMMITMENT

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ABSTRACT

Youth development in Indonesia is guided by Law Number 40/2009, which requires programs implemented across ministerial public institutions. However, realizing these ideals poses significant challenges, particularly in human capital development and the functioning of coordination mechanisms at national and regional levels. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of strategic planning, communication, inter-sectoral coordination, and human capital competencies on organizational performance, with commitment as a mediating variable in youth-serving organizations throughout Indonesia. This study used a quantitative approach, in which data were obtained through surveys of 232 administrators from three youth service organizations (West Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, and West Java Provinces), purposively selected from the total population of 552 throughout Indonesia. The data were processed using the SEM-PLS methodology. The findings indicate that strategic planning, internal communication, and human capital competence have a significant positive impact on strategic commitment and organizational performance. Strategic commitment has a significant direct effect on organizational performance and serves as a mediator between strategic planning, communication, and human capital competency. However, inter-sectoral coordination is not found to have a significant impact on strategic commitment or organizational performance, and it also fails to indirectly influence organizational performance through strategic commitment. These results suggest that internally based strategic capacity is more important than formal coordination structures in achieving organizational effectiveness. The study provides support for the centrality of strategic commitment to organizational performance.

KEYWORDS: Communication; Strategic Commitment; Organizational Performance; Strategic Planning.

1. INTRODUCTION

The need for investment in young people's development to secure long-term national competitive advantage, social inclusiveness, and economic sustainability has been recognized as growing within policy communities. In Indonesia, it is manifested in Law of the Republic of Indonesia number 40 of 2009 concerning youth, which sets regulations for youths to be aware of and understand sustainability, and requires the Indonesian state to pay more attention to socialization and the empowerment of sectors in which this sustainability exists. Even after supplementing with the Youth Development Index (YDI) to track policy progress, existing indicators reveal persistent implementation challenges. The rate of youth unemployment is a toxic 13.41 per cent, which is more than double the national average, with over half of employed youth engaged in informal or casual jobs. These patterns are symptoms of inefficiency in policy transmission from institutional design to the labour market and manifestations of structural weakness in organizational performance with respect to youth service provision (ILO 2022).

Inter-sectoral Nature of Implementation for Youth Policy in Indonesia. The plan requires inter-sectoral cooperation among relevant ministries in education, labour, social protection, health, and entrepreneurship. This relates to the fragmentation of youth services, in which Presidential Regulation (Perpres) No. 66 of 2017, reinforced by Perpres No. 43 of 2022, calls for an integrated coordination strategy for youth services. Independently, observations from the coordination meetings that the Ministry of Youth and Sports organized to share empirical data showed that attendance was irregular, institutional follow-up was low, and group accountability was weak. These findings are supported by contemporary reviews of public governance that argue that formal instruments of coordination may not perform unless they are underpinned by internal strategic and organizational capacity and commitment (Peters, 2018; Christensen et al., 2016; Christensen & Læg Reid, 2020).

However, although a great deal of collaborative governance literature has developed in the youth policy arena, previous Indonesian youth policy research still remains descriptive and tends to focus on regulatory settings, program outputs, and organizational determinants for effective coordination. Previous research on public sector performance has shifted from structural explanations to strategic and behavioral factors, such as the quality of planning, communication processes, human

capital capabilities, and commitment mechanisms (Bryson et al., 2018; Bryson et al., 2022; Andrews et al., 2017; Arend et al., 2017). This indicates a significant under-researched issue in the literature on how such internal factors impact organizational

Performance in inter-sectoral youth service provision settings in developing countries. Specifically, in reference to modern strategic management and public administration theory, we could argue that strategic planning offers a clear sense of goals and policy direction; communication promotes common understanding and mitigates coordination failure; human capital competence (HCC) enhances implementation capacity; inter-sectoral coordination constitutes structural fit; and strategic commitment serves as the micro-process through which strategy is impacted on organizational performance (Sulaimiah et al., 2024; Semenova et al., 2021; Díaz-Fernández et al., 2014; Garcia-Perez et al., 2019; Kasemsap, 2016). By grounding these five variables empirically, the article provides a context-rich explanation of why youth policy implementation fails in Indonesia and reveals theoretical and practical levers to enhance organizational performance within inter-sectoral youth governance.

There are, however, some important gaps that persist despite the flourishing of research on youth policy, collaborative governance, and public sector performance. One, much of the existing Indonesian youth development literature focuses on associated regulatory frameworks, program coverage, or macro-level policy outcomes, with relatively little attention given to empirical analyses of organizational determinants of performance in inter-sectoral youth service collaborations. Second, the literature on coordination effectiveness in the public sector frequently focuses on inter-sectoral coordination as a structural or procedural issue but pays little attention to the internal strategic and behavioral means by which coordination translates into performance outcomes (Taaffe et al., 2023; Eriksson et al., 2020; Page et al., 2018). Additionally, although recent work in strategic management and public administration has illustrated the significance of the quality of strategic planning, communication processes, human capital competence, and organizational commitment (Makhanya, 2024; Nofrisel et al., 2024; Al-Qudah et al., 2020; Oliveira & Honorio, 2020), together these variables are rarely amalgamated into a single empirical model in the specific context of youth service organizations in developing countries. This study fills these gaps by developing and empirically testing an integrated

model that centrally positions strategic commitment as a key intervening mechanism linking strategic planning, communication, human capital competence, and inter-sectoral coordination to organizational performance. What is new in this research is the empirical evidence from Indonesia, which considers a context-specific issue and shifts the coordination debate from structural compliance to strategic and behavioral performance drivers.

In light of these lacunae, this study aims to explore the direct and indirect impact of strategic planning, communication, human capital competence, and inter-sectoral coordination on organizational performance in youth service organizations, with strategic commitment as a mediating factor. In addition to the empirical contribution, this study has several theoretical and practical implications. Conceptually, it also contributes to the literature on contemporary public management and strategic governance by embedding constructs traditionally associated with strategic management into the analysis of inter-sectoral youth policy implementation (Peters et al., 2017; Vandermorris, 2020). From a policy point of view, the findings provide evidence-based knowledge on how to improve service delivery demand from young people, rooted in internal strategic capabilities, and then focus on imperative legal coordination requirements (OECD, 2019). Furthermore, the research's overall findings support better youth governance, resulting in a set of actionable trigger factors for improving organizational performance, which in turn lead to better labor market outcomes and beyond, including aiding the sustainable development goals of youth development in Indonesia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory states that organizational performance depends on the effective utilization of internal strategic resources and external structures (Rainanto et al., 2025; Barney et al., 2021; Pee & Kankanhalli, 2016; Bryson et al., 2007). RBV theory offers a strong logic for why organizations operating according to rules produce different performance outcomes. Organizational resources, including strategic planning, communication, human capital capabilities, and intersectoral coordination, are mediating drivers that can add value when integrated through strategic commitment as a fundamental dynamic capability necessary for executing strategy (George et al., 2022; Kohtamäki et al., 2012).

The performance of public organizations (OP) encompasses effectiveness, efficiency, service quality, accountability, and societal impact, rather than merely financial performance (Harini et al., 2023; Khaltar & Moon, 2020; Said et al., 2016). Recent public management literature indicates that performance dispersion is more determined by strategic focus, managerial capability, and internal coordination than by budget size or formal authority (Kuncoro et al., 2025; Rosenbloom et al., 2022; Bryson & George, 2020). This view is especially pertinent to youth-serving organizations; the effectiveness of programs is dependent on interagency collaboration and organizational commitment.

Strategic Planning (SP) is a core organizational resource embedded in RBV. The underlying assumption of this view is that SP is an organization's fundamental resources that provide direction, emphasis, and cohesion to its actions. These include experiential evidence of strategic planning, which establishes a greater sense of commitment to the strategy direction for an organization, reduces uncertainty, and engenders shared ownership over what is strategically important (George et al., 2019; Cronley & Kim, 2014). Organization members are more likely to apply resources and effort to pursuing a strategy if they perceive it to be rational and feasible (George, 2021). Therefore, SP not only enhances commitment to strategy but also directly affects organizational performance by aligning resources with strategy (Habeeb & Eyupoglu, 2024; Nafari & Rezaei, 2022).

Communication (COM) serves as a relational asset that supports the alignment of action, sharing learning, and sense-making across organizational boundaries. Recent research shows that effective communication enhances strategic commitment by establishing trust, strengthening shared vision, and fostering mutual understanding among organizational members (Saragih et al., 2026; Tola, 2018; Widyanti, 2020). For performance, communication contributes to decision quality, policy coherence, and service outcomes in inter-organizational networks (Farmansyah, 2020; Luoma-aho & Canel, 2020). RBV argues that value is created through communication, which is institutionalised and strategically, rather than ad hoc, underpinning both commitment and organizational performance.

Inter-sectoral coordination (ISC) is conceptualized as a strategic necessity to address wicked problems, despite the general governance scholarship of late acknowledging that 'coordination structure' would contribute little to increased organizational performance without facilitative

internal capabilities (Najafi et al., 2023; Peters, 2017).

Empirical evidence also shows that collaboration strategically promotes commitment, in the sense of collective ownership and shared responsibility among participants (Abate & Adamu, 2021; Bouckaert, 2010; van Schoor & Luetge, 2019). Coordination also improves organizations' work by linking activities, preventing duplication, and enabling resource sharing among agencies (Molenveld et al., 2020; Gautam, 2020). ISC is a structural construct of the RBV that can be operationalized as behavioral constructs acting strategically towards common organizational performance ends.

Human capital competence (HCC), as a critical strategic resource, is the firm's ability to implement complex strategic mandates. Recent studies on human capital highlight that competence influences strategic commitment, promoting employees' trust, engagement, and long-term commitment to organizational goals (Eskindarov et al., 2020; Skorkova, 2016; Alolayyan et al., 2021). Moreover, HCC is positively associated with organizational performance, as it enhances problem-solving, flexibility, and service quality (Salman et al., 2020; Knies et al., 2024). RBV insists that enterprises lacking adequate HCC cannot translate strategic intentions into sustained organizational performance.

Commitment strategic (CS), in turn is a key mechanism by which organizational resources are associated with performance. The literature has long noted that strategic commitment (SC) can boost Organizational performance by fostering continuous effort, voluntary behaviour, and alignment between strategy and action (Mendez & Avellaneda, 2023; Boukamcha, 2023; Ghumiem & Alawi, 2022; Silitonga et al., 2020). Apart from having a direct effect, CS also has a mediating capacity that enhances the organizational performance effectiveness of SP and communication, as well as HCC energy, and promotes ISC.

The mediating role of commitment strategy (CS) in the relationship between communication and organizational performance has empirical support as well, where high communication leads to increased commitment and ultimately to better organizational performance (William et al., 2012; Park, 2020). Similarly, commitment strategic (CS) also acts as a mediator between human capital competence and organizational performance by translating skills and capabilities into enduring organizational endeavour (Bektiarso, 2022; Permana et al., 2021; Raineri, 2017). Strategic commitment has an indirect impact on organizational performance through strategic

planning, as it fosters shared perceptions of strategic understanding and a continued implementation focus (George et al., 2019; Ali, 2018). And inter-sector coordination has organizational performance implications for strategic commitment: coordinating without such commitment could result in only symbolic compliance rather than substantial outcomes (Darham et al., 2022; Masri et al., 2025).

Strategic commitment (CS) is a key mechanism linking organizational resources to performance. CS can improve organizational performance by encouraging sustained effort, voluntary behavior, and alignment between strategy and action (Mendez & Avellaneda, 2023; Boukamcha, 2023; Ghumiem & Alawi, 2022; Silitonga et al., 2020).

In addition to its direct effect, CS also plays a mediating role in enhancing organizational performance through SP and communication, as well as energizing HCC and encouraging ISC. The mediating role of CS in the relationship between communication and organizational performance also has empirical support: high communication leads to increased commitment and ultimately better organizational performance (William et al., 2012; Park, 2020). CS also acts as a mediator between human capital competencies and organizational performance by translating skills and abilities into sustained organizational efforts (Bektiarso, 2022; Permana et al., 2021; Raineri, 2017).

CS has an indirect impact on organizational performance through strategic planning, fostering shared perceptions of strategic understanding and a sustained focus on implementation (George et al., 2019; Ali, 2018). Intersectoral coordination has implications for organizational performance, particularly regarding strategic commitment: coordination without such commitment can yield only symbolic compliance rather than substantial results (Darham et al., 2022; Masri et al., 2025).

Therefore, this study develops an integrated model showing that strategic planning, communication, human capital competencies, and intersectoral coordination act as strategic resources, with their influence on organizational performance both direct and indirect through commitment strategies.

This framework addresses the structures of dominance and priority in public management studies, calling for a theory-based explanation of intersectoral performance that goes beyond structural coordination to encompass strategic and behavioral mechanisms (Andrews et al., 2017; Bryson et al., 2018).

Figure 1 shows the theoretical framework of this

study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework.

The following research hypotheses are based on the literature review:

- H1:** Strategic Planning has a positive effect on Strategic Commitment.
- H2:** Communication positively affects Strategic Commitment.
- H3:** Inter-sectoral Coordination has a positive effect on Strategic Commitment.
- H4:** Human Capital Competence has a positive effect on Strategic Commitment.
- H5:** Strategic Planning has a positive effect on Organizational Performance.
- H6:** Communication has a positive effect on Organizational Performance.
- H7:** Inter-sectoral Coordination has a positive effect on Organizational Performance.
- H8:** Human Capital Competence has a positive effect on Organizational Performance.
- H9:** Strategic Commitment has a positive effect on Organizational Performance.
- H10:** Communication affects Organizational Performance, mediated by Strategic Commitment.
- H11:** Human Capital Competence affects Organizational Performance, with Strategic Commitment as the mediating variable.
- H12:** Strategic Planning affects Organizational Performance, mediated by Strategic Commitment.
- H13:** Inter-sectoral Coordination has an effect on Organizational Performance, mediated by Strategic Commitment.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study aims to analyze the impact of strategic planning, communication, intersectoral coordination, and human capital competence on an organization's performance improvement, with commitment strategy as the mediating variable. The research used a quantitative design and was conducted from December 2024 to February 2025. I analyzed this study conducted by the Ministry of Youth and Sports, which covers all provinces in Indonesia. The study sample comprised 232 employees from the team secretariat in West Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, and West Java, totaling 552 people who serve to coordinate the youth service across Indonesia (working staff).

Three provinces, i.e., West Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, and West Java, were selected as cases based on theoretical and empirical arguments. These provinces are distinct regional environments in Indonesia with diverse administrative capabilities, socioeconomic conditions, and development challenges for young people. First, West Java is a densely populated province with relatively strong institutional infrastructure, while West Nusa Tenggara and Maluku are provinces with low to moderate administrative capacity and certain geographical constraints. Such adjustment, in turn, allows for an analysis of how strategic planning, communication, and human capital competence-building, as well as inter-sectoral coordination, are functioning within different institutional

environments (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). In addition, those were provinces where there was ongoing ISC activity at the time of the study to ensure the availability of data; similarity or uniformity in policy implementation structures across organizations, and comparability.

A purposive type of convenient sampling technique was adopted, selecting only those respondents who possessed relevant knowledge and had been exposed to the issues under investigation to achieve the objectives of this study. If properly planned, purposive sampling is also particularly suited for organizational and policy implementation work, since informants should have experience with strategic planning processes, inter-sectoral coordination mechanisms, and performance management practices (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Employees not involved in inter-sectoral coordination activities or in the strategic decision-making process carried out by Diaspora are therefore excluded from the sample under investigation. Random sampling was not favoured, as it would include potential participants with little exposure to the coordination processes, leading to associated measurement error and a loss of explanatory power.

Scales previously used in empirical studies were modified to develop the construct instrument for this research, while ensuring content validity and theoretical relevance. All constructs were measured with multi-item scales that have already been widely used in organizational and public-sector research, and only minimal adaptation to the Indonesian youth service governance setting was required, without altering their inherent conceptual meaning. Organizational Performance (OP): The 12-item scale was borrowed from Bouckaert and Van Dooren (2015). It measures efficiency, effectiveness, productivity, service quality, and accountability in public organizations (e.g., "The efficiency of bureaucratic work processes is done through the optimal use of resources and increasing productivity"). The construct of Strategic Commitment (SC) had 9 items (Cohen, 1996), which were adapted from the scale that measured affective, normative, and continuance commitment to strategy implementation (e.g., "My team means to me that I understand support intend to implement [the organization's strategy in a loyalty sense]"). Inter-sectoral Coordination (ISC) was measured with 9 items drawn from Peters et al. (2017). Strengthening inter-sectoral coordination and governance for the effective implementation of Nepal's NDCs based on a voluntary national quality-of-governance standard for forest sector activities and programmes. Asia-

Pacific Network for Global Change Research, which measures the coordination and harmony of roles and actions between agencies (e.g., "Inter-sectoral coordination is needed to integrate harmonious efforts in achieving a common goal").

Strategic Planning (SP) was operationalized with 8 items adapted from Habeeb and Eyupoglu (2024) that reflect strategic clarity, comprehensiveness, and alignment between strategic plans and their specific operational programs (e.g., 'Strategic planning initiatives are developed to serve as operational guidelines for youth development programs'). Human Capital Competence (HCC): An 8-item HCC scale from Semenova et al. (2021) measures knowledge, skills, flexibility, and problem-solving ability of human resources (e.g., 'The organizational capability related to HR can address the youth-related challenges in the province'). Communication (Com) was measured using 8 items based on Palttala and Vos (2012) that captured openness, quality of communication, and inter-institutional information sharing (e.g., "Communication is transferred in efficient ways"), each rated on a five-point scale. All the measures used a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree), reflecting the perceptual nature of these constructs, and this scaling allows future comparison with other related constructs adopted from organizational research.

We use PLS-SEM based on the procedure outlined by Hair et al. (2021). The steps for using this method are (1) to define a structural model, (2) specify the measurement model, (3) collect and analyze data, and (4) this methodological transparency strengthens the validity and reliability of relationships between constructs in the research model at a more robust theoretical level through deeper statistical exploration of empirical data. The composition of the inter-sector coordination team on youth service providers among study participants showed that 172 people (74%) were male and only 60 people (26%) were female. The most common age group is 50–59 years (103 persons, 44%), and the least common is 30–39 years (49 persons, 21%). Most members are married (189 persons, 81%) and divorced (4%). According to the education data, 127 people (45%) have bachelor's degrees and 105 individuals (55%) have Master's degrees. In terms of employment experience, 124 (53%) have been working for 20–25 years, and 20% have been in their current job for 25–30 years or more. Most of the members are in job category IV 162 (70%), and 30% are in job category III.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In PLS-SEM, an outer loading is used to assess

each indicator's validity separately, based on its construct. The findings indicate how well the measurement items or indicators represent constructs such as strategic planning, communication, inter-sectoral coordination, human capital competence, and strategic commitment, which are linked to organizational performance. Regarding strategic planning, the highest loading as an outer loading of the item "strategic planning is formulated in detail" was identified. Strategic updates were the least affected/pushed back ('strategic updates have been adjusted to internal capabilities and the external environment'). There was high loading of the item "communication has attracted the attention of other institutions" and low loading for "communication is a method that is much more important in solving youth development". In terms of inter-sectoral coordination, "unity in action as a cross-sectoral principle" had the highest value, and "cross-sector coordination is important to integrate objectives" had the lowest value.

The outer loading with the greatest value for human capital competence was "HR has a system to appraise the expected competencies". "HR competency contributes to service quality improvement" had the lowest score. Regarding strategic commitment, "I think that this strategy will be successful" was the highest-scoring item, and "It is motivated to have a high commitment to a strategy"

was the lowest. In the case of organizational performance, "the organization has provided effective service quality" had the highest loading, and "the organization has served on the basis of relevance of problem" had the lowest loading. The strongest validity and construct explanation are provided by elements with the highest outer loadings, which validate measurement reliability across variables. From this model, reliability testing was performed to assess internal consistency of the indicators using AVE (average variance extracted) and Cronbach's alpha, a standard measure of construct reliability.

According to Hair et al. (2021), composite reliability estimates ranging from 0.60 to 0.70 are acceptable for exploratory research, and estimates around 0.70-0.90 suggest satisfactory data properties in this context. Convergent Validity is evaluated using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which indicates the extent to which indicators of a given construct are associated. Table 1 indicates that the CA and CR values of SP, Com, ISC, HCC, SC, and OP all lie between 0.60 and 0.90, indicating satisfactory internal consistency. Moreover, the AVE ratios across all constructs are above 0.50, indicating that each scale explains over half of the variance in its indicators and meets the requirements for convergent validity and a stable measurement model (Hair et al., 2021).

Table 1: Convergent Validity Value.

Variabel (numbers items)	Loading Range	CA	CR	AVE
Strategic planning (8)	0.762 - 0.804	0.909	0.926	0.612
Human capital competence (8)	0.632 - 0.713	0.840	0.874	0.616
Communication (8)	0.637 - 0.790	0.870	0.899	0.531
Inter-sectoral Coordination (9)	0.625 - 0.761	0.860	0.889	0.501
Strategic Commitment (9)	0.698 - 0.846	0.900	0.919	0.558
Organization Performance (12)	0.633 - 0.791	0.909	0.923	0.502

Source: Research Results (2025).

Discriminant validity tests that each construct is different from the others in the model (Hair al., 2021). This research uses the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), a suitable technique for assessing discriminant validity. When the HTMT value is less than 0.90, reflective measures are more effective at

discriminating between constructs. Table 2 (HTMT values of less than 0.90 for all constructs have been shown above), suggesting strong discriminant validity between the constructs in the current study, which exceeds the desired criteria.

Table 2: Htmt Value.

	Com	ISC	HCC	OP	SC	SP
Communication (Com)						
Inter-sectoral coordination (ISC)	0.886					
Human capital competence (HCC)	0.697	0.887				
Organization performance (OP)	0.842	0.800	0.845			
Strategic commitment (SC)	0.804	0.829	0.802	0.833		
Strategic planning (SP)	0.696	0.559	0.621	0.610	0.698	

Source: Research Results (2025).

Having established that strategic planning, communication, inter-sectoral coordination, human

capital competence, strategic commitment, and organizational performance are both valid and

reliable, it is now appropriate to test the structural model. This test measures the predictive power of the model and the interrelation among constructs in predicting the dependent variable. R^2 is an estimate of how well the endogenous variables predict the endogenous constructs, i.e., the amount of variance explained by the exogenous constructs (Hair et al., 2021). The R^2 is between 0 and 1; larger values indicate a stronger strength of association: it measures the proportion of variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the

independent variables. Typical values for R^2 are from 0.75 (substantial) through 0.50 (moderate), and down to 0.25 (weak). As shown in Table 3, strategic planning, communication, interoperability, and human capital competency are the "most significant" predictors of strategic commitment, with 75% significance. In contrast, when all these constructs are considered together, they could explain 88% of the variance in organizational performance, indicating that other elements may have a significant influence on the variation (Hair et al., 2021).

Table 3: Determination Coefficient Value.

Dependent Variable	R^2	R^2 Adjusted
Strategic commitment	0.747	0.743
Organisation performance	0.881	0.878

Source: Research Results (2025).

The structural relationships between the hypothetical constructs were tested using SEM-PLS. The relevance of these coefficients was tested using the bootstrap approach, which yields standard errors (SE), empirical t-values, and p-values for all path

coefficients. According to Hair et al. (2021), to indicate a relationship that is statistically significant when the empirical t-value surpasses 1.96 ($t > 1.96$, $\alpha = 5\%$) and the p-value is inferior than .05 ($p < .05$). The significance of the direct effect is reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Direct Effect.

Hypotheses	Original sample	Standard deviation	t-value	p-value
Strategic planning - Strategic commitment	0.140	0.042	3.309	0.001
Communication - Strategic commitment	0.253	0.093	2.732	0.007
Inter-sectoral coordination - Strategic commitment	0.045	0.112	0.400	0.690
Human capital competence - Strategic commitment	0.541	0.080	6.750	0.000
Strategic planning - Organisation performance	0.430	0.032	13.450	0.000
Communication - Organisation performance	0.178	0.056	3.115	0.002
Inter-sectoral coordination - Organisation performance	-0.031	0.056	0.554	0.580
Human capital competence - Organisation performance	0.168	0.063	2.652	0.008
Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.330	0.058	5.698	0.000

Source: Research Results (2025).

The results indicate that strategic planning, communication, and human capital competencies have direct effects on strategic commitment, which are consistent with hypotheses H1, H2, and H4. The results indicate that employee strategic commitment is positively affected by strategic planning, communication, and the development of human capital competencies, confirming all three hypotheses.

Other findings indicate that strategic planning, communication, human capital competence, and strategic commitment significantly influence organizational performance (supporting H5, H6, H8, and H9). The t-values exceeded the 1.96 cutoff, and the p-values were below 0.05, indicating a significant association between these dimensions. Therefore, these hypotheses are accepted. On the other hand,

the findings indicate that inter-sectoral coordination has no significant impact on strategic commitment and organizational performance. The path coefficient from inter-sectoral coordination to strategic commitment is near zero ($\beta = 0.045$, $p = 0.690$), indicating no substantial association in the sample. Similar to the leadership-organizational performance relationship, the negative relationship is insignificant and statistically non-significant ($\beta = -0.031$, $p = 0.580$). These results validate that, in isolation, inter-sectoral coordination has no impact on strategic commitment and organizational performance, thereby refuting H3 and H7.

Furthermore, Table 5 presents the results of the structural model test examining the hypothesized construct variables' indirect effects. The test results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Indirect Effect.

Hypotheses	Original sample	Standard deviation	t-value	p-value
Communication - Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.084	0.037	2.245	0.025

Human capital competence - Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.179	0.046	3.896	0.000
Strategic planning - Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.046	0.015	2.992	0.003
Inter-sectoral coordination - Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.015	0.036	0.407	0.684

Source: Research Results (2025).

Indirect relationships: Table 5 presents the results for the indirect relationships among the hypothetical constructs (i.e., Hypotheses H10-H13). From the analysis, hypotheses H10, H11, and H12 are found to have significant indirect effects, leading to their acceptance, whereas hypothesis H13 is rejected because it shows no significant indirect effect. More specifically, the structural model shows that communication, human capital quality, and strategic

planning are positively related to organizational performance through strategic commitment. The empirical t-values are greater than 1.96 (>1.96 ; $\alpha = 5\%$), and the p-values are less than 0.05. Overall, Hypothesis 13 (H13) is unsupported, indicating that strategic commitment does not mediate the relationship between inter-sectoral coordination and organizational performance.

Table 6: Comparison Of the Indirect Effect and the Direct Effect.

Hypotheses	Direct effect	Indirect effect	P-value
Communication - Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.178/3.115	0.084/2.245	0,025
Human capital competence - Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.168/2.652	0.179/3.896	0,000
Strategic planning - Strategic commitment - Organisation performance	0.430/13.450	0.046/2.992	0,003

Source: Research Results (2025).

Indirect and direct effects are compared in Table 6. The value of t for the indirect effect from hypothesis 11 (strategic commitment) is higher than that for hypothesis 8, suggesting that strategic commitment fully mediates the positive relation between human capital competence and organizational performance. In the meantime, with respect to the direct effects of H5 and H6, their t-values are larger than those for the indirect effects of H10 and H12, indicating that strategic commitment partially mediates them.

Key findings reveal that organizational performance in Indonesian youth service institutions is largely driven by internal strategic resources rather than formal inter-sectoral networks. Therefore, policies are needed that optimally utilize internal strategic resources to improve organizational performance. The findings also indicate that strategic planning, communication, and human capital competencies are positively related to strategic commitment, which in turn is positively related to organizational performance (Barney et al., 2021). Therefore, policy reforms are needed to enhance internal strategic capacity within public organizations, aligned with similar regulatory and coordination directives.

Strategic planning fosters strategic commitment, which can strengthen organizational goals and bridge the gap between long-term objectives and day-to-day tasks. When strategies are perceived as credible and feasible, organizational members are more likely to invest effort in implementation,

thereby strengthening commitment to priorities (Bryson et al., 2022; George, 2021). Communication also strengthens this process by enabling shared understanding and reducing ambiguity during implementation. Communication, as a relational term, can facilitate coordination of actions and understanding of meaning, with positive effects on commitment and performance outcomes (Dehghan & Ma'toufi, 2016; Kim et al., 2022). Therefore, organizations need to reform existing policies to increase members' active participation in positive communication.

Human capital competence is found to be the strongest predictor of strategic commitment and organizational performance. This is consistent with the RBV propositions that capable, adaptive (human resources) are important for operationalizing strategic intent into sustained performance (Barney et al., 2021; Shoaib et al., 2021; Ricardianto et al., 2021; Aman-Ullah et al., 2022). The complete mediating effect of strategic commitment in the human capital-performance link suggests that competence delivers performance value only when it is imbued with psychological bonding and voluntariness in the implementation of organizational strategies. In comparison, inter-sectoral collaboration does not have a significant direct or indirect impact on either strategic commitment or organizational performance. After the values of the coefficients, hovering close to zero for a model that essentially produces only formal compliance tools with no added value. Through an RBV lens, inter-sectoral

coordination constitutes a structural resource whose potential has not been achieved due to the lack of robust internal capacities and resolve (Xinyu, 2023; Peters, 2018; Sienkiewicz-Małyjurek, 2022). Examination of other recent empirical research indicates that these findings are similar to previous public management research, which demonstrates that strategic planning, quality communication, and human capital capacity better predict performance than the use of formalized coordination mechanisms (Andrews et al., 2017; Bryson et al., 2018). Although the literature on collaborative governance commonly takes for granted positive effects of inter-organizational coordination, this study accords with recent empirical findings that coordination in itself does not lead to performance improvement absent internal strategic alignment and commitment (Christensen et al., 2016; Jennings & Ewalt, 1998; Johansson et al., 2016).

5. CONCLUSION

This study sought to gain insights into the influence of strategic planning, human capital competency, inter-sector coordination, and communication on the performance of youth service organizations, as mediated by strategic commitment. Results indicate that strategic planning, human capital capability, and communication significantly contribute to increased strategic commitment and, eventually, to superior organizational performance. Strategic commitment was found to be a main mediating factor, once again underlining the need for individual motives and involvement to be in synergy with organizational goals. However, there was no

evidence of any direct or indirect (mediated) effect from post-development/cooperation interventions on disaster. Inter-sectoral in the programme due to bureaucratic complexities, lack of synergy, and an implementation gap.

In theory, this study contributes to our understanding of the relationship among different elements of management from the perspectives of strategic planning theory, goal-setting theory, strategic alignment theory, human capital logic, and communication theories. It also underlines that employee commitment, competence development, and internal alignment are critical drivers for efficient performance in the public sector. The results imply that youth service organizations need to commit to accurate strategic planning, effective communication mechanisms, and human resource development to strengthen the impact of strategic commitment on performance. Policy-wise, that means breaking down bureaucratic silos and fostering a culture of inclusion, accountability, and empowerment within public service entities.

The current study has some limitations. It is a case study of a non-profit youth services agency working in a given organizational and cultural dynamic that may not be translatable to others. Such relationships should be further studied in other public service settings and cultural contexts, including designs that are longitudinal to reveal causality over time. Moreover, a more in-depth analysis of the preconditions and machinery for effective inter-sectoral coordination has the potential to generate important knowledge about how public administration can be reformed.

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